

ANALYSIS OF THE GENDER CONCEPT FROM A RELIGIOUS ASPECT USING THE EXAMPLE OF UZBEK CULTURE

Rakhmatullayeva Umida Khamidovna

National University of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek
Interfaculty English Language Department, Faculty of Foreign Philology

Email: umidakhon88@gmail.ru

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19388041>

Keywords: *stress, depression, meditation, productive*

Currently, under the influence of globalization worldwide, the active participation of women and girls is sharply increasing in the fields of healthcare, science-education, culture, sports, social, economic, and many other areas, as well as in state governing bodies and the government system. Women are gaining various opportunities to work alongside men in all spheres and to hold leadership positions.

The concept of "gender" first appeared in the work of Simone de Beauvoir, who used it productively to express the position of women in society, stating that "a woman, from a socio-cultural perspective, is entirely similar to men; they differ only in their anatomical state". There are sufficient reasons to say that works related to the gender issue manifested even before the emergence of the feminist movement. Such is V. von Humboldt's work "On the Difference of Sexes and Its Influence on Organic Nature". In 1968, psychologist R. Stoller used this term to distinguish "masculinity" and "femininity" as socio-cultural characteristics "typical for men" and "typical for women." Using this term, R. Stoller emphasized that one can speak about male and female sex, and also stated that one can discuss masculinity and femininity without implying their connection to anatomy or physiology. In his opinion, these two realities (sex and gender) may be completely unrelated to each other, while also being defined independently of one another.

Since the formation of Islamophobia - fear of Islam - in the West, a misconception has been shaped in Western thought about the limited participation of Muslim women, their excessive attachment to their husbands, their adherence to old-fashioned ways in daily life, and especially their wearing of closed clothing. However, in Muslim countries, family ties are much stronger compared to non-Muslims, women's productive state is higher, and parent-child relationships are also close and stable. Our observations and analyses through new media tools – social networks – led us to connect the fact that in the West, people have a great need for psychologists, constantly engage in meditation with temporary effects, and take many sedative and calming medications due to stress and depression, generally feeling more unhappy, with a weakness in religious will. For a person with Islamic ethics does not fall into stress in various problematic situations – they are patient, grateful, and content. They put their trust in God. Analyzing the gender issue from a religious aspect, in Eastern countries, the upbringing of a daughter is approached more seriously than that of a son. The proverbs "He who does not beat his daughter beats his knee" and "The whip came from Paradise" are not without reason. Islam knows well how to raise people. It is also not a usual practice for fathers to have open conversations with their daughters on any topic or for them to be in free communication with their father. Although Mirzakarimboy loved his daughter, because he was a "Muslim father" and a "dignified man," he did not talk much with his daughter, just ordered some chores, saying "my

child." He knew that raising a daughter quickly and marrying her off at an early age was an "obligation" for every Muslim father.

What is the difference between the family and death of Anna Karenina from the great Russian writer Lev Tolstoy's "Anna Karenina" and Kumushbibi from A. Qodiriy's Days Gone by. According to the depiction of the two writers, both of these women are extremely beautiful, both have love, and both are victims of love. Both works conclude with the deaths of these two heroines. But are their loves and fidelity to family the same? Anna – a married woman – fell in love with a stranger. As a result, she killed herself. Her one sin became two. Kumushbibi – an innocent woman. She is faithful to her lawful husband. She even makes her co-wife jealous. What closeness is there in the fate of the causes of these two women's deaths – Anna's lover (not her husband!) and Kumush's co-wife – Zaynab? None at all! We cannot find a fate like Kumush and Zaynab's in European life. "...the body of Anna, who had just been full of life's vigor, now lay on the morgue table, before the eyes of strangers, shamelessly smeared with blood all over; her intact temples, her disheveled head, her heavy braids thrown back; her beautiful face, with half-closed red lips, had a pitiful expression, and her open eyes held a terrifying one. Special attention and emphasis are given to the depiction: "Anna's body lay shamelessly smeared with blood all over." The body of a woman who, under the pretext of love, betrayed her family and lived a shameless life, also lay before the eyes of strangers in a shameless state. There are sharp differences in understanding the family issue between Muslims and non-Muslims. "...Haji came and sat at Kumush's head. Otabek and his mother were standing. Kumush's eyes were closed, her hair was disheveled over her face. Haji himself arranged her hair and saw Kumush's bluish face and pressed her forehead... - Mother... Mother! - said Haji. Kumush opened her eyes, looked at him absentmindedly and, recognizing him... tried to rise. - Don't rise, mother... don't rise! Kumush's tears flowed down her temples... Haji, unable to restrain himself, wiped Kumush's tears and stroked her head: - God will grant healing, my child! Kumush convulsed into the bowl, Otabek came and supported her, Haji also held her head... This time it had turned into dark blood, and a few drops of blood also flowed from her nose... After vomiting, her eyes opened wide and she looked around restlessly: - Moth... fath.. - then, - my dear, - she groaned... She pressed her husband's face to hers, and closed her eyes as if ashamed...". Kumush "pressed her husband's face to hers, and closed her eyes as if ashamed..." This state is not an ordinary depiction of love; it is an expression of seeking her husband's consent even before her death. However, we must admit that the influence of new media tools, social networks, mass culture, women's social realization, being busy with work, are significantly impacting husband-wife relationships in the family, the changing position of women in the family, their free role, and their tolerance, and our attitude towards this situation is reactionary.

References:

1. Beauvoir S. de. The Second Sex. In 2 vols. Transl. by S. Franz. Vol.1, Vol.2: Facts and Myths. A Woman's Life. - M.: SPb.: Progress; Aleteyya, 1997. – 832 p.
2. Humboldt V. von. On the Difference of Sexes and Its Influence on Organic Nature // Language and Philosophy of Culture. - M.: Progress, 1985. – P. 142-154.
3. Kodiriy. Days Gone By, p. 148.
4. Stoller R. Sex, Gender and Society. - M., 1972. – P. 35-37.

5. Oybek. Blessed Blood, p. 64.
6. L.N. Tolstoy. Anna Karenina, p. 3.